

DESIGN FOR SAFETY: SYMBOL GENRE IN SAFETY SIGNS

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports on empirical research regarding the effectiveness of safety signs in an industrial setting as a function of the perceived risk imparted by symbols in safety signs. Symbols were compared according to the design genre of the figures in them. The hypothesis that an abstract or silhouette genre leads to a higher risk perception than other genres (neutral-realistic and caricature) was confirmed in an experiment conducted in an industrial plant, with plant workers as participants. This finding is analyzed and explained and general conclusions regarding the role of human factors in design are drawn.

Keywords: Design genre; Risk perception; Safety signs

INTRODUCTION

With drastic developments in technology, our environment is full of increased risks that are no longer necessarily self-evident, and we must find a way to warn against them. This is especially true in the context of the work place, and in particular the industrial plant. It is therefore mandatory to provide safety information in order to allow people to assess possible risks and, even more importantly, to impact their behavior such that they will avoid unsafe behavior. On the road and within buildings this is done primarily by the installation of safety signs. We approach the issue of safety signs from a Human Factors perspective which, we believe, is fundamental in design in general (Norman, 2002) and in signage in particular.

Signs may include text, but in many cases they rely primarily on symbolic representation in the form of symbols (visual images). Some safety symbols are universal, e.g., many road signs (stop, sharp road curves, etc.), poison, high voltage, and many more.

Other symbols are contextual and address specific risks in a particular environment. In this paper we shall address risks in a specific industrial context: a large laundry and sterilization plant that processes 45 tons of laundry for hospitals and clinics daily. Many risks along the processing lines must be considered; this study relates to eight such risks. For some of them, but not all, there were existing safety signs. For non-standard risks there are no definitive signage standards, resulting in existing signs that vary considerably and therefore workers cannot recognize them instantly.

Text in safety signage may pose a problem for a number of reasons: Some workers may not be proficient in the language used; Lengthy texts take long to read and therefore many people do not read them, at least not to the end; text in a large enough font requires a sizable sign, especially if the text is relatively long. This is one reason to integrate visual images or symbols in safety signs, as they are easier to remember (Leonard et al., 1999) and can replace a lot of text, and they do not require language proficiency; unlike text, symbolic language can be perceived in a glance. Whereas images are not meant to entirely replace text, a combination of a short text with an image/symbol allows for dual coding of the information (Pavio, 1975), wherein each mode reinforces the other.

The implementation of design tools may improve safety by improving visual access to safety signage, their comprehension and the level of perceived risk they impart, consequently promoting safe behavior (Parsons et al., 1999; Wogalter et al., 1997). In this study we address the image only, and ask: what is the best representation style for figures, and in particular human figures, in the design of safety signs? We identified four different genres that are commonly used to depict the human figure in visual safety information tools and wanted to find out

which genre is best comprehended and conveys the highest level of risk perception. These genres are: abstract, silhouette, neutral-realistic, and caricature. After a short literature survey we shall describe an experiment conducted in the industrial laundry mentioned above, in which workers served as participants. We report the results, before arriving at findings and conclusions.

LITERATURE SURVEY

The theoretical basis for our research starts with a model of information processing stages in warning obedience (C-HIP: Communication-Human Information Processing), developed by Wogalter et al. (1999). According to this model a source (regulatory authority etc.) uses an information channel (visual, auditory, etc., or a combination thereof) to broadcast safety information. At the receiver's end, processing this information occurs in overlapping and sometimes iterative stages: Noticing and attention, Memory and comprehension, effect of prior attitudes and beliefs, motivation, and finally, behavior. Failure at any of the stages may curtail the processing of this information. Warnings that include information representing the severity of possible consequences of a hazard impact positively the level of risk perception by the receiver (Young & Wogalter, 1998).

While ample research has been devoted to noticeability (e.g., Murray et al., 1998), attention (e.g., Wogalter & Leonard, 1999) or memory and comprehension (e.g., Mayhorn et al., 2004), few studies have examined the issue of risk perception, which greatly impacts attitudes and beliefs as well as motivation. We know that visualizing information is of great help in comprehending and assimilating it, as proven, for example, by researchers like Tufte (e.g., 1990) in the area of statistics. In safety signs the visual component is, or should be, dominant (Friedman, 1998; Leonard et al., 1999; Mackett-Stout & Dewar, 1981; Paivio, 1975), but studies have yet to address the issue of specific design genres used in the visual components of safety signs (image, symbol, pictogram). Previous research on noticeability and attention (Mackett-Stout & Dewar, 1981; Parson et al., 1999; Loring & Wiklund, 1988; Sanders & McCormick, 1993; Waters-Deppa & Martin,

1997) concluded that symbols that represent the human figure in an undefined and simplified form would elicit higher understanding and comprehension as well as noticeability and attention. This helped shape the notion that different design genres may generate different levels of risk perception and our research questions and hypothesis were formulated accordingly.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND HYPOTHESIS

Our central question in this research is:

- Do different features affect the level of perceived risk in safety symbols?

To answer this question we must first find out:

- Are there differences in the level of comprehension of the different design genres?
- Do the participants distinguish among the design genres?
- Which different features do the participants distinguish?
- What are the reasons for preferring each genre?

The hypothesis that was formulated based on the literature (see literature survey) regards the relationship between the design genre in a safety sign and the perceived risk, as follows:

- A representation of the human figure in an abstract or an unidentified silhouette in warning signs will be perceived as conveying higher levels of risk and warning credibility than a representation of an identified figure, whether neutral and expressionless or a caricature that expresses feelings.

In a descending order, the level of risk perception was believed to be highest for the abstract genre, followed by silhouette, realistic neutral and finally caricature. The hypothesis is based on studies that investigated visibility and attention to human figures that revealed a preference for full figures (black, no details).

In the following section we describe the experiment that was conducted in order to answer the research questions and test the hypothesis.

EXPERIMENT

The purpose of the experiment was to compare reactions to four design genres of the human figure in safety signs: abstract, silhouette, neutral realistic, and caricature, all of which are in use in signs today. Therefore the first step was to design four alternative symbols, each in a different genre, for each of the eight risks that were included in the experiment. Each symbol was displayed on a card measuring 7.3x7.3 cm (standard in similar experiments). Figure 1 serves as an example; it displays the designs for the risk: slippery surface.

Figure 1. Symbol design in four genres for risk: Slippery surface.

PROCEDURE

Participants responded to a questionnaire that was presented orally in individual interviews. The questionnaire consisted of three parts: a) Demographic information; b) sequence of assessment questions on symbols, for each of eight risks; c) Sorting task and preference questions. The questionnaire was administered to each participant individually; the duration of the interview was between half an hour and one hour. Each subject evaluated symbols for all eight risks in a Balanced Uniform Mix of two symbols from each genre. Utilizing a computerized algorithm, we set the genres and risk combinations so that every four subjects would be exposed to all 32 symbols.

PARTICIPANTS

44 laundry workers who had worked there for at least one month participated in the experiment. They were assigned to the experiment randomly by production managers, during working hours. To participate, workers had to express their consent and have normal eyesight. The age of participants ranged from 20 to 60; 54.5% were males and 45.5% were females. The majority of workers had no higher education: 18.2% were graduates of elementary school; 50% were graduates of high school. The mother tongue of 75% of the participants differed from the local language (Hebrew) and a knowledge level of the local language of 45.5% of the participants was self-reported to be intermediate or lower. A large percentage of those not proficient in the language spoke only Russian; therefore, a translator was used in the interviews with them.

VARIABLES

The dependent and independent variables include the following:

- Four design genres: Abstract, Silhouette, Neutral-realistic, and Caricature.
- Eight risk types: Slippery surface; Danger of injury from rising automatic conveyor belt; Prohibition of climbing on low automatic conveyor belt; Danger of injury to self or others resulting from high cart mobilization; Danger of injury from high hinged cart door; Ergonomic risk: proper lifting of laundry (straight back [I] and bent knees [II]); Danger of falling from an elevated plane; Danger of injury from a low lintel.
- Participants' prior awareness of and experience with the represented risk.
- Comprehension: this is a mediating variable, which is seen as a prerequisite for risk assessment. The independent variable is the symbols' design genre (4 categories), and the dependent variable is the risk perception. Most of the research deals with the impact of independent variables on this dependent variable. Another independent variable that effects the risk perception is the risk type (8 categories). Also taken into consideration were other intermediate variables, the level of comprehension of the symbol and the level of familiarity with the represented risk. Figure 2 summarizes the interdependence among the variables.

Questionnaire

Prior awareness and experience with risk, comprehension and risk perception were determined by scores using a Likert scale ranging from 0 to 8. Risk perception consisted of three questions: a) How dangerous is the depicted situation? b) Would a sign with this symbol cause you to be cautious? c) Is such a sign necessary in the laundry? A fourth question was added: d) Do you have experience with the depicted hazard? This question was needed for subsequent analyses (see results section).

To confirm the assumption that the design genres are indeed sufficiently distinguished and different from one another, a manipulation task was performed. Each participant received eight cards with symbols - two of each genre. The participant was asked to sort them into groups according to their design styles as he or she understands them (the genres were not introduced to the participants); the number of groups was left to the participants' discretion. Following the sorting task the participant was asked to explain why he or she chose the particular groups, and then was asked which group he or she preferred and why.

Figure 2. Research model: Interdependence among variables.

RESULTS

COMPREHENSION

In this preliminary phase of the experiment participants were tested for comprehension of the risks portrayed in the symbols. These were open questions, and three independent judges rated them as ‘correct’, ‘incorrect’, or ‘critical confusion’. The mean inter-rater agreement was 0.885. The comprehension thresholds for acceptance of a symbol are 67% according to ISO (International Organization for Standardization) and 85% according to ANSI (American National Standards Institute); critical confusion (when the subject's interpretation

is the opposite of the intended meaning) that is lower than 5% is also acceptable. As Table 1 shows, the level of comprehension in our experiment exceeded these threshold values. The only symbols that had a relatively low level of comprehension were the ergonomic ones (68.9 correct). It should be noted that the ergonomic risk symbols stood out since safety signs do not usually address ergonomic issues. Nevertheless, these results ensured that the experiment could be conducted as planned.

Reply	Percentage
Correct	91.3
Incorrect	7.6
Critical confusion	1.1
Total	100

Table 1. General comprehension scores

We also checked whether there were any differences in comprehension as a function of the design genres, and found that no significant differences existed.

RISK PERCEPTION

To examine the influence of genre and risk type on risk perception a two-way ANOVA was employed. Results indicated a significant main effect for Risk-type, and a significant main effect for Genre; the interaction between the two measures was found insignificant. Post hoc tests revealed that symbols representing the Ergonomic risk had a significantly lower mean score of Risk Perception than other types of risks. No other pairwise comparisons were significant. Figure 3 shows the participants' risk perception by risk type, and Figure 4 shows the risk perception by design genre.

Since the ANOVA results showed that there was a significant effect of Risk type on Risk Perception, we decided to use a one-way analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) in which the independent variable was the Genre (four categories), and the dependent variable was the factor score of Perceived Risk. We entered the type of risk, the comprehension score and the familiarity with the risk score as covariates. Results showed a significant effect for Genre. Indeed, Post Hoc analysis revealed that both the Abstract and the Silhouette genres received a significantly higher

mean score of Risk Perception than the Neutral-Realistic and Caricature genres, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Risk perception: Mean and standard error of the mean by risk type.

Two way ANOVA, Risk main effect: $F(7,320)=6.97, p<0.001$
 Risk type-Genre interaction was not significant: $F(21,320)=0.59, p=0.925$

Post-hoc (Tukey-HSD, $\alpha=0.05$) found that symbols representing 'lift with straight back' had a significantly lower Risk Perception score than other risks.

Figure 4. Risk perception: Mean and standard deviation of mean by design genre.

One way ANCOVA
 Genre main effect: $F(3,345)=9.77, p<0.001$
 Post-hoc (Holm's Seq. Bonferroni, $\alpha=0.05$) found that symbols from the Abstract and Silhouette genres had a significantly higher average Risk Perception score than the Neutral Realistic and Caricature genres.

SORTING AND PREFERENCE

The sorting task was meant to confirm that differences among the genres are indeed perceived

by the participants, and to this end each participant was asked to sort eight symbol cards into groups according to their design features. Genres were not mentioned, nor were there any instructions regarding the number of groups. 89% of the participants completed this task successfully, i.e., created four groups containing two symbols of the same genre each.

The questions: 'Why did you sort the symbols into these groups' and 'Which group is best' were open questions. Using card sorting and cluster analysis methods, evaluated by 5 judges (Everitt, 1993) yielding five response types, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Rationale for sorting of symbol cards

As Figure 5 shows, most participants' responses were directly related to design issues, but even participants who used clarity or comprehension, or who could not explain their choices, performed the task correctly for the most part.

When asked for their preferences, based on the groups they created, most participants chose the same groups that were also perceived, independently, as the most risky, see Figure 6 (those who preferred a group that was erroneous in the sorting task were classified as 'error' in this task). Further, participants were asked to explain their preferences, and the results are shown in Figure 7. The reasons are interesting and vary among the genres.

Figure 6. Preference of design genre

Figure 7. Rationale for genre preference

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

This research is based on the assumption that human factors considerations should guide design for people in general and safety signs design in particular. As assumed, results suggest that given high comprehension, symbols that aim to communicate safety information should preferably be represented with the design genres of Abstract or Silhouette, which are perceived as most “risky”.

We confirmed that participants in the experiment showed a high level of risk comprehension communicated by visual symbols and, at a later stage, it was found that participants naturally distinguish among design genres. This served to validate our tests of risk perception as a function of the design genre used to represent risks in symbols embedded in safety signs. The answers to our research questions are thus as follows:

- Are there differences in the level of comprehension of the different design genres?

- No, all design genres are well understood, and therefore a comparison among them is legitimate.

- Do the participants distinguish among the design genres?
 - Yes, participants naturally distinguish among design genres, even when they are not sure why.
- Which different features do the participants distinguish?
 - Participants distinguish clarity and comprehensibility, modes of human figure representation and facial expressions where relevant.
- Do different features affect the level of perceived risk in safety symbols?
 - Yes, a number of factors in the symbols affect the level of perceived risk, including comprehensibility, dangerous situation, facial expression (where relevant), and familiarity with symbol or symbol type.

We confirmed our main hypothesis, which was:

- A representation of the human figure in an abstract or an unidentified silhouette in warning signs will be perceived as conveying higher levels of risk and warning credibility than a representation of an identified figure, whether neutral and expressionless or a caricature that expresses feelings.

As Figure 4 demonstrates, the neutral realistic and caricature genres were rated relatively low for risk perception, whereas the abstract and silhouette genres rated high. The abstract genre was perceived as the riskiest, but the difference between it and that of the silhouette genre did not reach statistical significance. It turns out that the reason for this finding are quite complex, as evidenced by the reply to our last research question:

- What are the reasons for preferring each genre?
 - The abstract genre was preferred primarily because it expressed caution and danger, and because it was familiar. Comprehensibility contributed to a smaller extent. The silhouette genre was preferred

first because of its comprehensibility, and to a lesser degree due to the cautionary representation and familiarity. The neutral-realistic genre was preferred solely because it was comprehensible, and the caricature genre's preference stemmed almost exclusively from its facial expressions, with a small contribution of cautionary representation (see Figure 7).

The scope of this paper does not allow us to go into further details regarding our findings, but there is much to learn from this study not only about safety signs but about signs in general and even more universally about visual information communication. Our experiment highlights the need for visual symbols in signs, especially where text cannot be trusted as a communication channel for whatever reason. Because information communication is such a crucial ingredient of our lives, especially in the work environment, we conclude that much more attention should be devoted to questions related to information design, certainly where safety is at stake. As a consequence we recommend that human factors be given a much higher profile in design education than is currently the case. As a derivative, we think that visual perception, its causes and consequences, also deserve to be studied more rigorously by designers, and to this end cognitive psychology must be recognized as a most relevant discipline for design of any kind. Finally, we conclude that universal signs, for which comprehensive standards must be developed, are not enough. Further signage must be custom designed, based on particular contextual needs.

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